

THE FIRST FORMATION PROCESSES OF UZBEK VOCAL PERFORMANCE

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information on the history of the early formation of Uzbek vocal performance, the principles of vocal music pedagogy, the principle of sequence and continuity in education, the unity of artistic-musical and vocal technical principles, the principle of individual approach, and the achievement of regular perfection. given

Keywords: vocal, vocal performance, music, principle, culture, lesson, art, student, higher education institutions.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts[1]. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “Kokand” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [2] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [3]. Pupils should learn local styles in music by comparing them with dialects of local people, local clothes, instruments, words, dances, methods, actions, customs, local musical styles specific to these regions. some samples of the their performance styles, the state of performance, the most important features, the singers, poets, various ceremonies and the specifics of the sayings that exist in the places where they live they should learn performance features, and music teachers should conduct special research, meetings, roundtable discussions with students and organize musical trips to institutions where famous folk groups have performed.

Regarding the elements of uzbek vocal art and its first roots dating back to very ancient times, the art history expedition of Uzbekistan was conducted by B. Turgunov, Sh. Pidaev and others around Old Termiz and, moreover, Dalvarzintepa and Northern Bactrian culture. It provides very valuable information on the art of vocal singing in the architectural monuments found in the excavations carried out for the study.[4]

The history of the musical instruments depicted in the found architectural monuments shows that it dates back to the 1st-2nd millennium BC.

Vocal music culture has gone through its long and fruitful development paths during these difficult and turbulent times. In addition, although in those centuries, as the spiritual wealth of the population, it served for goodness and development, marking its glorious historical path.

For these aspects, we are very rich, colorful, echoing from the historically distant past, wide-ranging, colorful in style, the value is truly priceless and glorious, the rise of the Uzbek musical heritage, the music of the peoples of the world. Shown its significant influence in culture.

In fact, first in Central Asia, before Islam and its wide spread, “Seven makom” came in the Middle Ages, and “Twelve makom”, which was considered to be the pinnacle of the classical music culture of the uzbek and tajik peoples and a high example of creativity is a wonderful musical system, based on it, Bukhara Shashmakom, Khorezm makom series and Ferghana-Tashkent makoms, folk music, traditional performance, dostan and dombira art, changgobuz,

flute, trumpet. ways, compositional creativity, bakhshi-poet, jirov and terma creativity have developed and are developing rapidly as the branches of our musical culture.

It is known from history that the musical heritage of the Uzbek people is limited to certain situations and circumstances, passed down from mouth to mouth, from teacher to student, from father to son, from mother to daughter (family ceremony, seasonal ritual, labor songs and religious sayings), free themes (lapar, yalla, terma, song) and epics, works of classical status - works of many musical genres, such as Shashmakom, Tashkent-Fergana status, Khorezm status has been ensuring the traditionality and sustainability of his art. Today, they form the basis of our national spiritual music values.

The main principle (principle) and methods of vocal music pedagogy. In the process of teaching vocal art to students, all singer-teachers are based on four main principles:

1. The principle of sequence and continuity in education.[5] This is a general pedagogical principle, which is based on the process of education from simple to complex. Continuity is also necessary in everything - both in expanding the range of the singer, in making the exercise more complicated, in choosing a repertoire, in spiritual experience - from lyrical to dramatic works (to the peak of emotions), the strengthening of the repertoire leads to the loss of the voice. In classes with students, you should worry about the quality of the sound, its pitch, vibration, and distance. It should not be allowed to strengthen the repertoire.

2. Artistic - the unity of musical and vocal technical principles. To train a singer according to the rules, it is necessary to solve two problems at the same time: to build a performance apparatus - that is, to make the singer a professional voice and to practice speaking in it. These two issues are implemented at the same time, depending on each other.[6] It is a big mistake to think that in order to perform elementary performance of any, even the simplest skill, it is necessary to process the voice first, and then master the performance skill. It is impossible to educate an actor-singer without it.

3. The principle of separate approach. A singer is a unique musical instrument. Everything is very special. Unchanging (dogmatic) instructions harm vocal pedagogy. the level of opportunity of each student is different, because the strength and endurance of his voice depends on his personal character. [7] In particular, it is necessary to know and pay attention to its spiritual characteristics, and not to exert too much spiritual influence on the voice. The student's character is clearly visible in all fields independently in the softness and breadth of the voice, strength, endurance, quality, and in talented, energetic, imaginative, willful young people. Therefore, the lessons should be conducted taking into account the above.

4. The principle of achieving regular maturity. This full moon has been voted for the last 15 years. If the student does not work independently, the knowledge given by the teacher in the training will not be useful to the student. In the final processes of education, special importance is given to the independent preparation of the student. A principle is a main idea, and a method is a way to achieve a goal. There are the following methods in vocal pedagogy:

1. Sound.
2. Based on experience (empirical).
3. Having one center (concentric) – Glinka's style.
4. Primary tone - German vocal school.[8]

Classical works, which are considered the foundation of national musical culture, are performed by students of higher and secondary special educational institutions, including

pre-school, extra-curricular, general secondary schools, academic-lyceum and vocational colleges. and promotion among undergraduate students, first of all, organization of teaching activities, making them enjoy the huge rare wealth of our nation, and the main thing is to ensure the continuity of musical traditions.

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